

Well	ExptType	Experiment	Sample	TargetType	Target	Status	Concentration	Supermix	CopiesPer20uLWell
A06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	NEG	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
A07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	NEG	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
B06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	1.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fI	OK	143	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	2860
B07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	1.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fI	OK	151	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	3020
C06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	2.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fI	OK	97	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	1940
C07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	2.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fI	OK	104	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	2080
D06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	3.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fI	OK	489	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	9780
D07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	3.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fI	OK	519	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	10380
E06	Absolute Quantification	ABS	4.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fI	OK	37	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	740
E07	Absolute Quantification	ABS	4.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6fI	OK	35.4	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	708
A08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	NEG	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
A09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	NEG	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
B08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	1.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
B09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	1.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	OK	132	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	2640
C08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	2.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
C09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	2.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
D08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	3.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
D09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	3.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
E08	Absolute Quantification	ABS	4.1	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	
E09	Absolute Quantification	ABS	4.2	Ch1Unknown	HPV16 E6I	CHECK	No Call	QX200 ddPCR EvaGreen Supermix	

TotalConfMax	TotalConfMin	PoissonConfMax	PoissonConfMin	Positives	Negatives	Ch1+Ch2+	Ch1+Ch2-	Ch1-Ch2+	Ch1-Ch2-	Linkage	AcceptedDroplets
				0	12962						12962
				0	14371						14371
		150	136	1512	11699						13211
		158	143	1661	12160						13821
		102	91	1177	13733						14910
		109	98	1197	13010						14207
		503	475	4961	9626						14587
		533	505	5514	9953						15467
		40.3	33.6	465	14568						15033
		38.7	32.1	450	14740						15190
				0	15951						15951
				0	16044						16044
				517	6452						6969
		139	125	1444	12159						13603
				8713	5713						14426
				9010	6145						15155
				10563	4722						15285
				10311	4776						15087
				3683	11762						15445
				3591	12056						15647

PoissonFractionalAbundanceMin	ReferenceAssayNumber	TargetAssayNumber	Threshold	MeanAmplitudeofPositives	MeanAmplitudeofNegatives
	1	1	0	0	7410.8
	1	1	0	0	6911.7
	1	1	9132	14599	7286.8
	1	1	8710	14923	6789.6
	1	1	8988	14886	7213.3
	1	1	8624	14719	6685.3
	1	1	9571	15173	7171.3
	1	1	9091	15251	6610.5
	1	1	8723	12863	7063.5
	1	1	8224	12844	6472.6
	1	1	0	0	4168.8
	1	1	0	0	3895.7
	1	1	6615	21019	3377.3
	1	1	7769	24014	3680.2
	1	1	8406	26156	4066.5
	1	1	8352	26336	3849.9
	1	1	8718	26243	4021.4
	1	1	8957	26437	3829.6
	1	1	8217	26259	4034.1
	1	1	7433	26255	3800.1

MeanAmplitudeTotal	ExperimentComments	MergedWells	TotalConfMax68	TotalConfMin68	PoissonConfMax68	PoissonConfMin68	TotalCNVMax68
7410.8							
6911.7							
8123.8					146.7	139.3	
7767					154.3	146.9	
7819					99.6	93.9	
7362.2					106.5	100.6	
9892.8					496	482	
9690.8					526	512	
7242.8					38.7	35.3	
6661.4					37	33.7	
4168.8							
3895.7							
4686.1							
5838.7					135.5	128.6	
17408							
17219							
19378							
19280							
9333.9							
8953.5							

